

Digital humanities and students of Latin

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1 What are the Digital Humanities, how I presented them to students in Zagreb, Croatia, and what have I found in the process?

Here is an answer to the first question, as given by Patrick Sahle in 2013. Sahle says that the digital humanities try to answer old questions with new tools; that the humanities transform into digital, while the digital has to adapt to the humanities.

Ten years before Sahle, John Unsworth saw Digital Humanities as a set of tools to ask new humanistic questions and offer new answers to our usual questions.

Ten years after Sahle and twenty years after Unsworth, what is the answer to the question about the Digital Humanities? Is it still the same?

My answer is necessarily modest: Digital Humanities is what people do with computers when they want to understand culture, society, art. The undertaking is different from what we usually do to understand culture, society and art because computers have changed both the objects of our study and how we look at them, how we approach and treat them. A series of transformations have happened in our field: transformations of sources, of texts that we think about, of translations that help us think about the texts. We do not understand these transformations fully yet, we only sense and feel that they are here. Nevertheless, our task as teachers is to show that to our students, even to confess that we do not know the answers. Our task is to give our students room to find their own answers.

2 Transformations and approaches

How are the sources transformed by the computers and the internet? There are suddenly so many of them, and they are completely different. Latin is not any more just a string of neatly printed words laid out in the textbook; we can look, and look in astonishing detail, at the words from which our textbooks, through efforts of philologists, were painstakingly produced. Today we enjoy the access that for centuries was reserved only for Herren Professoren. If you stop to think about it, it is quite exciting... but the access is only potential. Do we dare to use it?

Moreover, there are different possible approaches to our sources, and each is valuable in its own right; our students should explore at least two of them.

There is search – solving a problem, looking for something that we have already decided we want, like I have searched for a manuscript with the first decade of Livy. But there is also browse: we just look around, or fool around, without searching for anything in particular; we let something attract our attention and then we start to follow that lead.

There is also the difference between people who use the tools and those who build them. This difference is not so clear-cut – the programmers are users too, and the users can program as well. As digital humanists, we want to show these aspects, these sides of the same coin, to our students.

3 How do I use the notions of browse and search, of use and program?

I focus on transformations, and not only those changes that happen to people, but also on those that the people can do. I teach students how to use a concordance program on a Latin text, and I invite them to discuss how a text shows its different side when processed by the concordancer. Then we look at individual words. Looking them up in a dictionary is a basic philological activity, but with a computer this activity can be performed in at least two different ways. Why are they different? How are they different? What is better in the LiLa approach, which is radically different from Logeion's?

The Latin syntax is taught in Croatian schools and universities in a quite traditional way, which means that we usually mix syntax and semantics and approach the sentence in a linear way. Thanks to Perseids Project, I can present to my students a treebank view of the sentence. Even better, using the Arethusa interface in Perseids, the students can annotate sentences as treebanks ("treebank" them) on their own and share them as I am sharing them now. In Arethusa you meet playfulness as an important DH innovation:

thanks to the interface the words can be moved around, the sentence becomes alive or at least animated.

Our approach to translation is transformed too. An interface, again in Perseids, allows us to connect words of Latin texts with the words of their translations. There is nothing more. But the very exercise of accounting for every word makes us very much aware of our limitations, theoretical and practical, and of places where the languages do not fit perfectly.

Finally, the best opportunity I have had to test all the approaches was in a shared seminar that was taught both on line and in person. The lectures were given by various partners in the seminar, from c. fifteen universities, onlin, while the practical part and the discussions were in person. This format introduced to my students not only different aspects of the Digital Classics, but also different styles of teaching and (also important) different ways English is spoken around the globe.

4 What have I learned, and what do I wish I would have done more of?

The relatively simple tools I have presented are demanding; they transform the user into a so-called power user. They also engage people who are using them; the people can make something of their own, something new. Finally, what we do with the tools is a good starting point for reflection. We start to see how "variants" and "interpretations" of texts actually look like.

What have I not done?

I wish I have given my students more opportunities for browsing, for exploring freely, in an unstructured way: go and bring me something interesting!

I wish we had a chance to do some actual programming (with query languages, for example).

And I wish that the Sunoikisis seminar had found a chance for people to work together, not only to listen to lectures together. As we have learned, this has to be carefully prepared.

Unfortunately, I do not know the German educational system well enough to make comparisons. This is something that we can do together.

Thank you.